

MASTER'S THESIS

Interactive machine learning for music classification

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Abstract

Audio embeddings are a promising approach to music representation, in part thanks to their ability to extract complex patterns from audio data; the predictive power of audio embeddings is utilized for a semantically meaningful, two-dimensional visualization of music data in a user interface (UI) which has been developed as part of this thesis research. As a contribution to ongoing research on the intersection between music information retrieval (MIR) and interactive machine learning (IML), the UI allows users to iteratively train a classifier for numerous audio classification tasks. As part of this research, the certainty-based class prediction uncertainty (CPU) heuristic, and the dataset coverage (DC) heuristic are proposed; these heuristics are shown to identify informative samples in music collections, and their efficiency is objectively evaluated by means of simulated, iterative active learning (AL) classification tasks for 6 different embedding-dataset pairs. The objective evaluations have shown promising results, in which high classification accuracies are shown to be achieved in fewer iterations in AL classification tasks.

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The fruits of the music-human symbiosis are profound, and its echoes continue to inspire humankind to connect, find meaning, and do good. In part thanks to this symbiosis, we have been able to reach the current levels of societal and technological development. A guiding star and a faithful companion in our journey through life, it continues to patiently nudge humankind, to stay on track and be a meaningful part of this reality; *that is the beauty of music.*

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1 Introduction

In his manifesto on the strengths and limitations of contemporary music information retrieval (MIR) research, Widmer made an interesting point: *computers cannot distinguish between songs that an individual might find boring or interesting* (Widmer, 2016). Understanding individual preferences, which is necessary for answering questions of a nature similar to the one posed by Widmer in 2016, requires the consideration of a very wide range of factors, including cultural, educational, regional and social background, age, and even personality traits (Bogdanov, 2013; Matrosova, 2024), but also the highly dynamic nature of listener context (Ben Sassi & Ben Yahia, 2020).

In their works from the 2010s, both Bogdanov and Widmer have foreseen that computational algorithms will have a deeper understanding of music content and individual (contextual) music preferences (Bogdanov, 2013; Widmer, 2016). In line with this foresight, there currently exist deep learning-based methods which automatically process audio signals into semantically meaningful, lower-dimensional representations (Zaman et al., 2023); commonly referred to as *audio embeddings* (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023). Audio embedding models have the ability to extract highly complex patterns from audio data, and yield higher accuracies in classification tasks compared to traditional classification methods (Zaman et al., 2023).

The exceptional performance of audio embeddings in classification tasks form the core foundation on which this research is built; in this research, an interactive *user interface (UI)* is introduced, in which users are able to explore and annotate their music collections. The predictive power of audio embeddings is utilized for a semantically meaningful, two-dimensional visualization of music data, and it forms the basis for two ML-based heuristics which are proposed as part of this research; the certainty-based *class prediction uncertainty (CPU)* heuristic, and the *dataset coverage (DC)* heuristic.

In the UI, users can iteratively train a classifier which can return class predictions for audio files. Consistent with the *active learning (AL)* paradigm, the proposed heuristics highlight *informative* tracks which are suitable candidates for user annotation in order to train the classifier efficiently. By annotating informative data points, as opposed to random data points, high classification accuracies can be achieved within fewer training iterations (Joshi et al., 2012; Konyushkova et al., 2017). The efficiency of the CPU and DC heuristics in highlighting informative data points is reflected in promising results from AL simulations with a number of embedding-dataset pairs, carried out as part of this research.

By allowing the user to steer the classifier training process in accordance with their own personal taxonomies, this UI is a contribution to ongoing research on the intersection between MIR and *interactive machine learning (IML)*. Besides its contribution towards a better understanding of music collections, the identification of informative samples in music collections has the potential to advance musicological research through *efficient dataset creation*, among other useful applications. Furthermore, the UI is indifferent to both chosen audio embedding and provided music collection alike, granting users the freedom to inspect their music collections from different perspectives, while simultaneously accounting for future efforts made towards the development of general-purpose audio embeddings which achieve high accuracies in classification tasks (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023).

In this thesis document, the advantages and potential drawbacks of the proposed approach to music classification are discussed in detail, with the aim of shining a light on possible directions for future research in computational musicology. Lastly, there is an important nuance to point out; in this research, certainly not all of the musical understanding is offloaded to computational models and algorithms. *You*, the reader, have a crucial role to play as well. Therefore, I invite you to interact with the environment¹. I wish you a pleasant reading, and a fruitful journey in music exploration and understanding.

¹<https://github.com/danilkaru/interactive-ML-music-classifier>

2 Background

2.1 Audio embeddings

One of the major challenges in computational musicology is the development of data structures which appropriately represent music, and, more abstractly, encode musical meaning (Volk et al., 2011). A long-standing, related challenge in scientific literature has been the attempt to encode musicological and semantic information about audio files in descriptive representations (Serra et al., 2013). Even though audio files² accurately capture the linear progression of music pieces in the temporal domain, they do not implicitly encode abstract musical features such as genre, key, tempo and mood (Serra et al., 2013). Therefore, a common approach in the field of MIR has been the extraction of musical features at different levels of abstraction with the use of computational algorithms (Serra et al., 2013).

With the recent advancements in the field of deep learning (DL), a new, compact representation for audio has been widely researched in scientific literature, commonly referred to as *audio embeddings*. Audio embeddings are representations of audio signals with a relatively low dimensionality (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023), and they are generated from neural networks which are trained on audio datasets (Zaman et al., 2023), consequently capturing a multitude of complex musical features which are stored in a compact, vector-based form.

```
{
  "id": "reggae.00007",
  "genres": "reggae",
  "embedding": [
    0.005040863528847694,
    -0.020111406221985817,
    0.08041738718748093,
    0.0055677033960819244,
    -0.01155778206884861,
    -0.005170624703168869,
    0.031777385622262955,

```

Figure 1: Part of a CLAP audio embedding (Chen et al., 2022; Elizalde et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2024) representing the *reggae.00007* audio file from the GTZAN (Tzanetakis & Cook, 2002) dataset. The full embedding vector has a dimensionality of (1024,).

Audio embeddings have proven to be a very significant contribution to the field of MIR, in part due to their state-of-the-art performance in audio classification tasks (Zaman et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2025). Audio embeddings outperform traditional computational classification models, which typically rely on an intermediate manual or algorithmic music feature extraction step; audio embedding models, however, do feature extraction automatically, and are often able to capture more abstract patterns which can help with distinguishing between classes more accurately (Schmid et al., 2023; Zaman et al., 2023).

The performance of audio embedding models in classification tasks is dependent on the datasets which they are trained on; to ensure that high classification accuracies are achieved, audio embedding models must be trained on very large datasets, requiring significant computational resources and human annotation efforts (Zaman et al., 2023). However, after the model has been trained, class predictions for new input data can be retrieved with relatively simple classifiers such as shallow multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023; Schmid et al., 2023). Using knowledge from pre-trained models for downstream classification tasks is a concept commonly referred to as *transfer learning* (Van Den Oord et al., 2014).

2.1.1 Overview of existing audio embedding models

Current audio embedding models are generally part of one of two broad categories: *task-specific* audio embeddings, and *general-purpose* audio embeddings. A further distinction can be made with respect

².wav, .mp3, .ogg etc.

to the underlying neural network architectures in the embedding models; the majority of embedding models are based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), autoencoders, transformers, and hybrid architectures which integrate one or more aforementioned approaches (Zaman et al., 2023).

Task-specific audio embeddings are typically developed with the aim to achieve high accuracies in specific classification tasks; commonly researched directions include genre classification, mood classification, speech recognition, environmental sound classification, and more (Zaman et al., 2023). Examples of embedding models which achieved state-of-the-art classification accuracies in genre classification tasks include the CNN-based *musicnn* (Pons & Serra, 2019), and the more recent, transformer-based *MAEST* (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023) models. Both models were trained on large and annotated datasets under the supervised learning paradigm. Inspired by language learning in humans, Baevski et al. have attempted to create a model which can extract complex features from small datasets; the resulting, self-supervised *wav2vec 2.0* model achieved state-of-the-art performance in speech recognition classification tasks (Baevski et al., 2020).

A significant amount of research is also being dedicated to the development of *general-purpose* audio embedding models which can simultaneously address speech, audio event and audio tasks (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023). Measuring the performance of general-purpose audio embedding models is commonly done with the HEAR (Turian et al., 2022) and HARES (Wang et al., 2021) benchmarks (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023; Schmid et al., 2023), which cover a variety of audio classification tasks for speech, music and environmental sound (Schmid et al., 2023).

Examples of general audio embedding models include *CLAP*, introduced by Elizalde et al. in 2022, which is a model which produces embeddings from audio and text input; a key property of the CLAP model is its ability to understand audio through natural language, and vice versa (Elizalde et al., 2022). The CLAP model achieved state-of-the-art performance in 16 downstream tasks across 8 different audio domains (Elizalde et al., 2022). Efforts have also been made to fine-tune task-specific embedding models to achieve high performances in domains beyond the one which the model was originally trained for; in their 2022 research, Ragano et al. have successfully fine-tuned the *wav2vec 2.0* model to achieve high classification accuracies for music classification tasks (Ragano et al., 2022). More recently, Schmid et al. have introduced the *mn01*, *mn10* and *mn30* models, and succeeded in reducing computational resource demands compared to earlier general audio embedding models, while simultaneously achieving state-of-the-art performance in HEAR benchmark classification tasks (Schmid et al., 2023).

2.1.2 Latent space

A powerful property of audio embeddings is that their vectors can be seen as coordinates in a multidimensional, semantically meaningful *latent space*; embedding vectors of 'similar' music pieces have coordinates which are close to each other. Similarity of embedding vectors in the latent space is dependent on the chosen dataset and target classification task (Tahiroğlu & Wyse, 2024); for instance, if the model was trained to predict genres, then similarity in the latent space will mostly be related to genre.

The latent space of audio embeddings has a number of useful applications. One such application is the visualization of music; in 2022, Tovstogan et al. have introduced a user interface in which audio embeddings are reduced in dimensionality to a two-dimensional, semantically meaningful representation, allowing for exploration and rediscovery within music collections (Tovstogan et al., 2022). Similarly, Lanzendörfer et al. have introduced Audio Atlas, an interactive web application for the visualization of audio data using CLAP (Elizalde et al., 2022) embeddings (Lanzendörfer et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the latent space can also be used for creative applications; in their 2024 research, Tahiroğlu & Wyse have outlined the potential of latent spaces as a tool for computational music creativity, showing the possibilities for the exploration and subsequent sonification of regions in (con-

tinuous) latent spaces (Tahiroğlu & Wyse, 2024).

Consistent with ongoing efforts for understanding the inner workings of ML models, Zhang et al. have recently published a work on interpretability in audio embedding models; in their 2025 work, Zhang et al. aim to understand the semantics of audio data which is encoded in CLAP (Elizalde et al., 2022) embeddings (Zhang et al., 2025). Earlier works on audio interpretability have approached interpretability by highlighting features in spectrograms that significantly contribute to model decisions, exemplified by the 2019 research by Won et al., and observing the prediction output of ML models by passing large numbers of input data (Zhang et al., 2025).

2.2 Human-in-the-loop machine learning

A growing amount of research in the domain of machine learning is being carried out on the concept of *human-in-the-loop machine learning*, a subfield which is centered around the idea of human users interactively training machine learning algorithms (Mosqueira-Rey et al., 2022). The goal of human-in-the-loop machine learning is to integrate human knowledge, emotional state and practical capability with ML algorithms, such that algorithms are trained as quickly and effectively as possible, while still achieving good classification accuracies (Joshi et al., 2012; Konyushkova et al., 2017).

2.2.1 Active learning (AL)

Active learning (AL) is an approach by which annotation costs can be potentially reduced effectively (Wang et al., 2019). By means of selecting candidate data points for the iterative expansion of the training set which are most *informative* (Maia et al., 2024), active learning allows the training an algorithm as quickly and effectively as possible while still achieving good classification accuracies (Joshi et al., 2012; Konyushkova et al., 2017). To achieve this goal, active learning systems allow human 'oracles' to improve the learning process by providing labels to unannotated data in real time (Sarasúa et al., 2012; Mosquiera-Rey et al., 2022).

Algorithm 1 contains a general outline of an active learning loop, adapted from the 2007 research by Schein & Ungar and slightly adjusted:

Algorithm 1 Active learning (AL) loop

Require: Dataset consisting of labeled and unlabeled data (X, Y) , human annotator

- 1: Initialize training set $(X_{\text{train}}, Y_{\text{train}})$
 - 2: **while** Target classifier accuracy not reached **do**
 - 3: Calculate AL *heuristic* values for all unlabeled samples
 - 4: Highlight top k samples as candidates for annotation in accordance with heuristic (X_k)
 - 5: Let human annotator annotate the highlighted k samples (Y_k)
 - 6: Add annotated samples to the training set $X_{\text{train}} \leftarrow X_{\text{train}} + X_k, Y_{\text{train}} \leftarrow Y_{\text{train}} + Y_k$
 - 7: Train classifier on $X_{\text{train}}, Y_{\text{train}}$
 - 8: **end while**
-

An important premise of the AL paradigm is that, rather than augmenting the training set of the classifier with random samples, the classifier will reach some acceptable accuracy faster by selecting the most informative samples at every training iteration i , and adding them to the training set of the classifier at the next iteration $i + 1$ (Schein & Ungar, 2007).

The informativeness of samples in AL is often quantified through *heuristics*; samples which are highlighted by a heuristic are considered to be suitable candidates for the expansion of the training set in future AL iterations (Konyushkova et al., 2017). One of the most common AL heuristics is the minimization of class prediction uncertainty in classifiers; samples which have a high class prediction uncertainty get highlighted as candidates for addition to the training set in future iterations (Konyushkova et al., 2017). This approach to AL is referred to as *certainty-based AL* (Shuyang et

al., 2017). In their 2012 research on AL for personalized music emotion recognition, Su & Fung have implemented a variation of this heuristic, in which the training set is extended with instances which have a class posterior probability closest to 0.5 (Su & Fung, 2012).

Similarly, Du et al. have connected informativeness with prediction uncertainty in their 2015 paper on strategies for improving AL algorithms (Du et al., 2015). In their paper, Du et al. refer to the *best-versus-second-best* (BvSB) method, in which for every unannotated data point, the delta between the two highest posterior probabilities of a binary/multi-label classifier prediction is considered as a measure of uncertainty (Du et al., 2015). Thus, the smaller the delta between the two highest posterior probabilities, the higher the prediction uncertainty for a given data point can be considered to be. The BvSB measure tends to select candidate points which have the property of being close to the hyperplane which distinguishes two or more classes (Du et al., 2015).

Additionally, several AL heuristics which are not certainty-based have been proposed in literature; in their 2012 research, Joshi et al. have proposed a heuristic which maximizes coverage of training points in a dataset, ensuring that all points have a nearest labeled data point within some bounded distance (Joshi et al., 2012). Moreover, data-driven approaches to AL have been proposed, in which candidate sample selection strategies are *learned* based on experience from previous AL outcomes; in their 2017 research, Konyushkova et al. have trained a regression model which for data points can predict the expected error reduction at a particular iteration in an active learning loop (Konyushkova et al., 2017).

2.2.2 Interactive machine learning (IML)

Interactive machine learning (IML) is another approach towards human-in-the-loop machine learning (Mosquera-Rey et al., 2022). The IML approach builds upon the principles of AL, but is a more *human-centered* approach; in the AL paradigm, the human annotator needs to label highlighted samples, and repeat this task for a prolonged time, as a result of which human factors such as distraction and fatigue can come into play (Mosquera-Rey et al., 2022). In IML environments, however, the human annotator is not necessarily required to only annotate highlighted data points, and human annotators can interact with the environment beyond the annotation loop, in a freer and less structured manner (Mosquera-Rey, 2022).

2.3 Existing work on AL/IML and audio

The potential of applying AL for MIR tasks has been identified as early as 2012 by Sarasúa et al., in which they used active learning techniques for music mood classification tasks (Sarasúa et al., 2012). Sarasúa et al. have employed different selection strategies, and their findings included the importance of choosing data points such that the whole dataset space is covered (Sarasúa et al., 2012), an idea which has been also central to the coverage-based heuristic as proposed by Joshi et al. in their 2012 research (Joshi et al., 2012).

In 2019, Wang et al. have developed a sound classification model to detect artifact noise in sound recordings from the Sounds of New York City (SONYC) project, an initiative for mitigating urban noise pollution in New York City (Wang et al., 2019). The aim was the identification of an sound artifacts, in which 15 human annotators were helped by certainty-based AL heuristics (Wang et al., 2019).

In their 2021 research, Hilasaca et al. have proposed a visual framework for data annotation; in the visual framework, audio files are clustered based on extracted numerical features, and subsequently presented to the user in an interactive 2D space, allowing the user to explore and label soundscape ecology³ data, as part of a long-term ecological research project in the Cantareira-Mantiqueira corridor in Brazil (Hilasaca et al., 2021).

³The academic study of acoustical patterns which are emanated from landscapes (Pijanowski et al. 2011)

3 Heuristics for (re-)annotation and classification tasks

As part of this research, two heuristics has been implemented, with the aim of assisting the user in classification and (re-)annotation tasks by highlighting suitable candidates which are to be added to the training set in AL loops. Consistent with the AL paradigm as introduced in section 2.2.1, these heuristics aim to identify samples which are most *informative* with certainty-based and non-certainty-based approaches.

3.1 Class prediction uncertainty (CPU)

The *class prediction uncertainty (CPU)* heuristic is a certainty-based heuristic, in which candidates are highlighted based on the uncertainty in the posterior probability distribution of the classifier. Consistent with the best-versus-second-best (BvSB) method, the uncertainty in the posterior probability distribution is defined as the delta between the probability values of the two classes with the highest estimated probability (Du et al., 2015).

Consider, for some classifier, the posterior probability distribution to be $[p_1 : 0.7; p_2 : 0.1; p_3 : 0.2]$, then the CPU heuristic will assign a value of $p_1 - p_3 = 0.5$, signifying low uncertainty. If the posterior probability distribution is $[p_1 : 0.507; p_2 : 0.491; p_3 : 0.002]$, then the CPU heuristic will assign a value of $p_1 - p_2 = 0.016$, signifying relatively high uncertainty. The samples with the highest uncertainty are chosen as candidate samples for annotation in future iterations.

3.2 Dataset Coverage (DC)

The *dataset coverage (DC)* heuristic is a non-certainty-, coverage-based heuristic, which highlights tracks based on their cosine distance to the nearest point which has been annotated with a class label. The heuristic builds on the hypothesis by Joshi et al. and Sarasúa et al. from their 2012 research, which states that, given a dataset which contains informative samples, coverage is an important factor which can contribute to a good distribution of training samples (Joshi et al., 2012; Sarasúa et al., 2012).

The following code block contains pseudo-code for a possible implementation of the DC heuristic:

```
minimum_distances = []
for data point i in dataset
    if i is not annotated
        cosine_distances = []
        for j in annotated points
            distance = cosine(i, j)
            cosine_distances.append(distance)
        minimum_distances.append(min(cosine_distances))
    else
        minimum_distances.append(-1)
```

Unannotated samples (i) which have the largest minimum cosine distance to their annotated neighbors (j) are considered as the most suitable candidates for annotation.

4 User Interface

For this thesis, an interactive user interface (UI) has been developed, which allows individuals to visualize and explore a two-dimensional embedding representation of their music collection of choice. The UI allows the user to iteratively (re-)annotate/(re-)classify music tracks, and this user annotation data is used for teaching an interactive ML model to provide increasingly accurate class predictions in real-time.

Figure 2: *The initial UI environment state as seen by the user after starting the application (first release version 1.0.0, Safari browser, July 2025).*

4.1 Dash Plotly

The UI application consists of a front end and a back end which has been developed with the use of *Dash Plotly*, a versatile framework for the development of data visualization applications with the use of Python (Plotly, 2025). In earlier research, the Plotly library has been used by Tovstogan et al. in 2022, for the visualization of deep audio embedding spaces (Tovstogan et al., 2022). Dash applications are built around two central concepts; the app *layout*, and *callbacks* (Plotly, 2025).

Dash Plotly app layout

The Dash app *layout* is responsible for handling the visual components of the application (Plotly, 2025). The Dash framework offers a wide variety of HTML-, CSS- and JavaScript-based components, which can be generated with a few lines of Python code. Besides pure HTML components, which can be found in the *dash.html* module, the *dash.dcc* (Dash Core Components) module features premade interactive components such as buttons, input fields, graphs, and many more (Plotly, 2025).

Integral to the proper functionality of the UI is the *dash.dcc.Graph* component, which is used for the visualization of the embedding space of a provided music collection using a 2D scatter plot. In addition to the visualization of data, the *dash.dcc.Graph* component also handles interactive selection of data by the user, allowing the user to select points in the 2D embedding space.

```

html.Div([
    # Class name; input field and assign button
    html.Div([
        dcc.Input(id='class-name', type='text', placeholder='Enter Class Name', style={'marginRight': '10px'}),
        html.Button('Assign Class', id='assign-class', n_clicks=0),
    ], style={'marginTop': '15px', 'marginBottom': '0px'}),
], style={'marginTop': '15px', 'marginBottom': '0px'}),

```

Figure 3: Dash components for handling user input, part of the full Dash app layout of the UI. The user can enter the class name of choice in an input text field ($id='class-name'$), and click a button ($id='assign-class'$) to assign the provided class to a selection of data points.

Dash applications consist of multiple (nested) components, and most of the components must be assigned with a component ID, which ensure that components are connected to Python functions. For instance, with the components as shown in figure 3, text input submitted by the user is used for further processing in a higher-level Python function⁴ which handles the assignment of class names to data points in the 2D music embedding space. The real-time interactivity of Dash Plotly applications is in large part made possible thanks to *callbacks*.

Dash Plotly callbacks

The Dash framework features *callback functions*, which are automatically called whenever the state of some application component changes (*input*), in order to update the state of another component in the application (*output*) (Plotly, 2025).

```

@app.callback(
    Input("audio-play-select", 'value')
)
def set_audio_play(input_audio_play_selection):
    if input_audio_play_selection == "Yes":
        config["play_audio"] = True
    else:
        config["play_audio"] = False

```

Figure 4: Callback function for activating/deactivating audio playback on hover.

Figure 4 contains an example Dash callback function which is responsible for handling the status of audio playback in the UI. Any time that the state is changed in the 'audio-play-select' (radio button) component, this function gets called, which yields an update of the audio playback Boolean value in the UI settings configuration file. Subsequently, all functions and components which depend on the updated Boolean value are also updated automatically; the automatic 'reaction' of outputs to changes in inputs are a core concept in the paradigm known as *reactive programming* (Plotly, 2025).

4.2 Setting up the UI

The UI can be installed on a local device by cloning into the Github repository associated with the UI⁵. Python 3.10 must be installed on the local device to ensure proper functionality.

After cloning into the repository, it is recommended to create a virtual environment for the installation of all necessary Python dependencies. After opening a command-line interface (CLI) and changing to the directory in which the repository has been installed, you can run the following commands; `conda create -n IMLMusic python=3.10 -y`, then `conda activate IMLMusic`, then `pip install -r requirements.txt`. Subsequently, the UI software can be run from the CLI with `python [DIRECTORY/TO/UI/REPO/user_interface.py]`.

The UI is now locally hosted and accessible with any browser on `http://127.0.0.1:8050/`.

⁴assign_class in app_callbacks.py, see Github repository

⁵<https://github.com/danilkaru/interactive-ML-music-classifier>

4.3 UI fundamentals: a basic music classification loop

This subsection contains a concise overview of steps which are needed to train a classifier for personalized music classification.

Step 0: Converting the music collection to audio embeddings

Prior to interacting with the UI, the user is expected to generate a *.json* file with audio embeddings for their music collection of choice. Users can use any embedding model for audio data, however, for a music collection consisting of N songs, the generated file must adhere to the following structure:

```
[
  {
    "id": "unique_song_id_1",
    "genres": "genre/label/mood_1",
    "embedding": [[...], [...], ...],
    "bpm": 70.0
  },
  ...
  {
    "id": "unique_song_id_N",
    "genres": "genre/label/mood_N",
    "embedding": [[...], [...], ...],
    "bpm": 167.0
  }
]
```

Each entry in the array of dictionaries represents a single track from the music collection, with the following keys:

- “*id*”: A unique identifier for the song (string).
- “*genres*”: A descriptor such as genre, label, or mood (string).
- “*embedding*”: A list (or NumPy array) of one or more embedding vectors (list of floats).
- “*bpm*”: The tempo of the track in beats per minute (float). This value is used for visualization purposes.

A *.ipynb* file for generating an embedding *.json* file can be found in the Github repository associated with this research. With this file, it is possible to generate CLAP (Elizalde et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2024) audio embeddings for a provided audio file directory.

Step 1: Visualizing the music collection

To visualize the music collection, the user must upload the *.json* embedding file to the user interface. This can be done by clicking on the “Upload Embedding JSON File” button, or by simply drag and dropping the relevant file on the button. The music collection is then presented to the user as an interactive representation of an audio embedding space, with the UMAP (McInnes & Healy, 2018) technique used to reduce the dimensionality of the audio embeddings onto a 2D surface.

Figure 5: 2D representation of a MAEST (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023) embedding space generated from a 300-song subset of the MusAV dataset (Bogdanov et al., 2022). A part of the collection has already been annotated by the user.

By default, the size of the data points is predicated on the embedding variance, a metric which, for every audio file, represents the spread of scalar values in the averaged out embedding vector. The values are normalized to a range which ensure that the data point sizes do not impact visual presentability. The range values can be adjusted in config.py, and the data point sizes can be set to be dependent on BPM values, which are part of the embedding .json file as described in step 0.

The shape of the music data 'cloud' can be adjusted by changing the seed of the UMAP projection. This can be done in the config.py file, by changing the value of "UMAP_seed" in the ui_layout_config dictionary.

Step 2: Training the classifier, iteration $i = 0$

After the music collection has been visualized in the user interface, the user can now interact with the music collection, and moreover, the user can now annotate songs in the music collection in accordance with their personal taxonomies. The user can define their own list of classes, and assign those classes to (a subset of) the music collection. An ML-based classifier, more specifically a multilayer perceptron (MLP), can then be trained to predict the class of remaining unannotated data points.

When, according to the user, enough data points have been annotated, the user can train the classifier by clicking the "Train & Predict" button.

Figure 6: Classifier predictions for user-defined classes 'jungle', 'bossa' and 'techno' for a small music collection.

After the classifier has been trained, the predictions of the classifier will be displayed in the user interface; in the 2D plot, all unannotated data points are assigned with the predicted class and the corresponding color. Furthermore, tracks are assigned with a *track status*; the list of symbols associated with track statuses is outlined in the following figure:

Class	Total Tracks	Status Distribution
bossa	4	👤: 1 (25.00%), ✅: 3 (75.00%)
jungle	6	👤: 1 (16.67%), ✅: 5 (83.33%)
techno	5	👤: 1 (20.00%), 🤖: 1 (20.00%), ✅: 2 (40.00%), ❗: 1 (20.00%)

Status Symbols:

- 👤 - User annotation
- ✅ - Not marked as problematic
- ❗ - Marked as problematic by class prediction uncertainty (CPU) heuristic
- 🤖 - Marked as problematic by dataset coverage (DC) heuristic

Figure 7: Statistics for every class, associated with the classifier predictions as shown in the previous figure, along with an overview of track status symbols.

Some tracks are highlighted with additional symbols; tracks which are highlighted with the double question mark symbol have high class prediction uncertainty (CPU), and tracks with the double arrow symbol have a high (Euclidean) distance to the nearest annotated data point (DC). Tracks which are annotated by the user are highlighted with the person symbol, and tracks which are not highlighted by the heuristics do not get highlighted with a symbol in the 2D plot.

Step 3: Training the classifier, iteration $i \geq 1$

After the initial iteration of the music classification loop, the user can choose to either accept the classifications, or to continue the loop. If the user is not yet satisfied with the classifications as provided by the classifier, the user can choose to continue the music classification loop by expanding the training set with additional data points.

By adding the highlighted tracks to the training set in future classifier training iterations, it is hypothesized that the classifier is able to reach a higher classification accuracy within fewer training iterations. The user can also add other tracks to the classifier, or re-annotate classes which have been annotated in the initial iteration.

Step 4: Accepting the classifications

When the user is satisfied with the predictions of the classifier, the user can accept the predictions by clicking on the “Accept Predictions”.

Figure 8: Classifier predictions accepted.

The user can also download an overview of annotations and classifier predictions by clicking on the “Download results” button.

Audio previewing

An important addition to the UI is the implementation of *audio playback on hover*; by hovering over the data points in the 2D embedding space, users can playback the audio files which are part of the uploaded music collection. This can be done by providing the local folder path containing the audio files which have the same filename (without extension, e.g. .mp3/.wav) as the names stored in the *id* fields in the uploaded embedding file. Because the matching happens on *id*-strings and not on file paths, in principle, the user is free to pass a local folder path which contains alternative versions of the audio (e.g. full version, snippets, alternative mixes/masters, etc.). The audio playback on hover functionality has been proposed in earlier research, including the 2020 research by Tovstogan et al. on the the exploration of latent spaces of music collections (Tovstogan et al., 2020).

5 Methods

To quantify the relevance of the user interface, as well as the relevance of the proposed heuristics for improved music classification, *objective* and *subjective evaluations* are carried out as part of this research. In the objective evaluations, the heuristics are tested by means of simulated active learning loops. In the subjective evaluations, 4 participants are asked to interact with the user interface, and to answer a number of questions related to the user interface.

5.1 Objective evaluation

With the aim of quantifying the relevance of the heuristics which have been introduced in this research, an experimental setup is proposed in which active learning (AL) classification accuracies are measured for 3 different *active learning strategies*; expanding the training set with *random* samples, expanding the training set with candidates highlighted by the *CPU heuristic*, and expanding the training set with candidates highlighted by the *DC heuristic*.

5.1.1 Audio embeddings

The active learning strategies are simulated for 2 different audio embeddings;

- *MAEST* (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023);
- *CLAP* (Elizalde et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2024).

MAEST

The *MAEST* (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023) audio embeddings have been generated with the associated Github repository⁶. For this audio embedding, all audio files have been converted to mono format, with a sample rate of 16 kHz.

The *MAEST* model which has been used for embedding generation is *discogs-maest-10s-pw-129e*, and it requires an audio file to have a duration of at least 10 seconds. Furthermore, consistent with the findings by Alonso-Jiménez et al. that the middle blocks of the transformer in the *MAEST* model feature the best representation for downstream classification tasks (Alonso-Jiménez et al., 2023), the 6th transformer block is used.

The *discogs-maest-10s-pw-129e* *MAEST* model generates an embedding vector for every 10 seconds of audio. For audio files which are longer than 10 seconds, the embedding vectors are averaged out to yield one embedding vector with a dimensionality of (768,).

⁶<https://github.com/palonso/MAEST>

CLAP

The *CLAP* (Elizalde et al., 2022) audio embeddings have been generated with LAION-CLAP, a Github repository associated with 2022 research by Chen et al., and 2024 research by Wu et al.⁷. For this audio embedding, all audio files have been converted to a sample rate of 48 kHz.

LAION-CLAP offers the possibility to choose different pretrained checkpoints, however, within the scope of this research, the default pretrained checkpoint has been used. For every audio file, the LAION-CLAP model generates embeddings with a dimensionality of (1024,).

Embedding file structure

The embedding vectors are encapsulated in a .json file, as outlined in section 4.3. Besides the embeddings, an ID, genre/label/mood (descriptor) and a BPM is stored for every song. The ID and descriptor are retrieved from a .csv file which contains all song IDs and descriptors, and depending on the dataset this file can be generated programatically or manually.

5.1.2 Datasets

The active learning strategies are applied on 3 different classification tasks with the following datasets;

- *GTZAN* (Tzanetakis & Cook, 2002);
- *Moods MIREX* (Hu & Downie, 2007);
- *Freesound Loop Dataset* (Ramires et al., 2020).

GTZAN

The GTZAN dataset consists of 1000 tracks with a duration of 30 seconds, and the dataset has been created for genre classification tasks. The number of unique classes in the GTZAN dataset is 10.

Moods MIREX

The Moods MIREX dataset consists of 269 tracks, and the dataset has been created for mood classification tasks. The number of unique classes in the Moods MIREX dataset is 5.

Freesound Loop Dataset

The Freesound Loop Dataset consists of 9455 loops which have been retrieved from Freesound (Font et al., 2013). The number of unique classes in the dataset is 6. Before generating the embeddings for the Freesound Loop Dataset, a few data preprocessing steps have been applied. First of all, all tracks which have more than one label have been filtered out. After this step, only 28 loops with the class “vocal” remained, thus this class has been removed from the data. Next of all, all loops which have a duration of less than 10 seconds have been filtered out. After this step, the class with the least amount of remaining loops was “bass” with a loop count of 82. Therefore, the decision has been made to create a subset of 400 loops which are randomly sampled from the pool of 842 suitable loops.

The resulting subset consists of 400 samples; 78 “percussion” loops, 89 “fx” loops, 70 “bass” loops, 76 “melody” loops, and 87 “chords” loops.

⁷<https://github.com/LAION-AI/CLAP>

5.1.3 AL strategies

Six different active learning (AL) strategies are evaluated; in each strategy, unannotated data points, represented by audio embedding vectors which have been extracted from the associated audio files, are either randomly chosen, or chosen in accordance with the *class prediction uncertainty (CPU)* or *dataset coverage (DC)* heuristic, and subsequently added to an expanding training set in order to iteratively train a multilayer perceptron (MLP) classifier. Within the scope of this research, the AL strategy with random sample selection is referred to as *random baseline (RB)*.

For each chosen data point, the associated class label is extracted from the dataset, and subsequently the embedding-label pair gets added to the training set as training data. Thus, the class labels in the objective evaluation simulations are equivalent to the class labels which are found in the evaluated dataset.

The algorithm for the RB active learning strategy is as follows:

Algorithm 2 Random candidate sample selection

Require: Labeled embedding data (X, Y)

- 1: Let the user (re)label an initial subset $(X_{\text{init}}, Y_{\text{init}})$
 - 2: Initialize $X_{\text{acc}} \leftarrow X_{\text{init}}, Y_{\text{acc}} \leftarrow Y_{\text{init}}$
 - 3: **while** unlabeled samples $X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$ remain **do** ▷ All samples in X that are not in X_{acc}
 - 4: Select k random samples ▷ k is user-defined
 - 5: Add selected samples to $(X_{\text{acc}}, Y_{\text{acc}})$
 - 6: Train classifier on $(X_{\text{acc}}, Y_{\text{acc}})$
 - 7: Return label predictions for $X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$
 - 8: **end while**
-

The algorithm for the CPU active learning strategy is as follows:

Algorithm 3 Candidate selection based on minimization of class prediction uncertainty (CPU)

Require: Labeled embedding data (X, Y)

- 1: Let the user (re)label an initial subset $(X_{\text{init}}, Y_{\text{init}})$
 - 2: Initialize $X_{\text{acc}} \leftarrow X_{\text{init}}, Y_{\text{acc}} \leftarrow Y_{\text{init}}$
 - 3: **while** unlabeled samples $X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$ remain **do** ▷ All samples in X that are not in X_{acc}
 - 4: **for all** $x_i \in X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$ **do**
 - 5: $p \leftarrow \text{predict_proba}(x_i)$
 - 6: $\delta_i \leftarrow \frac{|p_{\text{max}} - p_{2\text{nd}}|}{p_{2\text{nd}}} \times 100$ ▷ Class prediction uncertainty
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Select k samples with the smallest δ_i ▷ k is user-defined
 - 9: Add selected samples to $(X_{\text{acc}}, Y_{\text{acc}})$
 - 10: Train classifier on $(X_{\text{acc}}, Y_{\text{acc}})$
 - 11: Return label predictions for $X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$
 - 12: **end while**
-

The algorithm for the DC active learning strategy is as follows:

Algorithm 4 Candidate selection based on maximization of dataset coverage (DC)

Require: Labeled embedding data (X, Y)

- 1: Let the user (re)label an initial subset $(X_{\text{init}}, Y_{\text{init}})$
 - 2: Initialize $X_{\text{acc}} \leftarrow X_{\text{init}}, Y_{\text{acc}} \leftarrow Y_{\text{init}}$
 - 3: **while** unlabeled samples $X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$ remain **do** ▷ All samples in X that are not in X_{acc}
 - 4: **for all** $x_i \in X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$ **do**
 - 5: Compute cosine distances to each $x_j \in X_{\text{acc}}$
 - 6: $d_i \leftarrow \min(\text{cosine_distance}(x_i, x_j))$ ▷ Dataset coverage
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Select k samples with the largest d_i ▷ k is user-defined
 - 9: Add selected samples to $(X_{\text{acc}}, Y_{\text{acc}})$
 - 10: Train classifier on $(X_{\text{acc}}, Y_{\text{acc}})$
 - 11: Return label predictions for $X \setminus X_{\text{acc}}$
 - 12: **end while**
-

In the CPU, DC and RB strategies, the training set is randomly initialized, and it is not guaranteed that all class labels occur in the initial training set. Therefore, 3 additional AL strategies are evaluated in which the initial training set of the CPU, DC and RB strategies are initialized with stratified sampling, ensuring that every class label from the dataset occurs at least once in the initial training set. Within the scope of this research, these strategies are referred to as RB (S), CPU (S) and DC (S).

Additionally, in the objective evaluation of CLAP and the Freesound Loop Dataset, a theoretical approximation of an upper bound of classification accuracy is calculated, in this research referred to as the *hybrid-one-look-ahead (HOLA)* algorithm. At every iteration of the objective evaluation simulation, the HOLA algorithm looks ahead one iteration, and simulates the classification accuracies which are returned if candidates are chosen in the next iteration based on the CPU or the DC heuristic; the aim of the HOLA algorithm is to maximize the classification accuracy in a greedy best-first approach. The accuracies returned by the HOLA algorithm represent the potential classification accuracy improvement which is feasible to achieve, under the condition that at every iteration, the 'right' candidate samples are added to the training set.

5.2 Subjective user evaluation

Within the scope of this research, subjective evaluations of the UI are carried out, both for providing insights into the user-centeredness of the current implementation of the UI, as well as for answering the proposed hypotheses in this research with more data at hand. In the subjective evaluations in this research, 4 participants interact with the UI to complete some amount of iterations for different

classification tasks, after which they are asked to evaluate the process and the resulting classifications by means of a Likert scale questionnaire. The music collections are chosen by the participants, and they are assisted in creating .json audio embedding files.

5.2.1 Questionnaire

	Range	Step size
<hr/> <i>Questions about the user interface</i> <hr/>		
Q1: Interacting with the user interface was enjoyable;	[1, 7]	1
Q2: Interacting with the user interface was easy;	[1, 7]	1
Q3: The buttons in the user interface have a clear purpose;	[1, 7]	1
Q4: The datatables were a useful addition to the user interface;	[1, 7]	1
<hr/> <i>Questions about the music embedding space</i> <hr/>		
Q5: Similar music pieces are close to each other in the interactive music data 'cloud';	[1, 7]	1
<hr/> <i>Questions about the classifier and heuristics</i> <hr/>		
Q6: Musically speaking, the classes predicted by the classifier for unannotated data make sense to me;	[1,7]	1
Q7: Musically speaking, in the classifier probability distribution, the classes predicted as second and third most likely class make sense to me;	[1,7]	1
Q8: The tracks highlighted by the heuristics matched your definition of difficult tracks;	[1, 7]	1
Q9: How many iterations did it require to reach an acceptable classifier performance?	[1,∞)	1

Table 1: Questions used for hypothesis testing

When participants answer 1 (strongly disagree) or 7 (strongly agree), they are asked to provide an additional elaboration for why they chose the rating. The questions as outlined in table 1 are grouped by category, and the ordering of the questions may differ in the interview.

5.2.2 Participants

Participant 1: Predicting subjective emotional depth in music

Participant 1 is a male participant from The Netherlands in the age group 18-24. The participant has proposed a classification task in which the classifier attempts to recognize nuances in perceived emotional depth in 98 songs from his music collection. Along with the list of songs, he provided annotations, in which every song is labeled as being part of class ED1, ED2, ED3, ED4, and ED5, where class ED1 describes songs which are perceived to be the least emotionally deep, and class ED5 describes songs which are perceived to be the most emotionally deep.

Participant 2: Predicting music preference

Participant 2 is a male participant from The Netherlands in the age group 25-34. The participant has proposed a classification task in which the classifier attempts to recognize music preference, described

by grades as class labels. The music collection consisted of 55 songs, and a file with song names and corresponding grades was created. In the interaction with the UI, songs were labeled with 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 or 9 as classes by the participant.

Participant 3: Distinguishing between Slavic languages

Participant 3 is a male participant from The Netherlands in the age group 18-24. The participant has chosen a classification task in which the classifier attempts to distinguish between 7 different Slavic languages. The audio collection contains excerpts from weather forecasts in Belarusian, Czech, Polish, Russian, Serbian, Slovak and Ukrainian, split into 10 audio chunks of approximately 4 or 5 seconds for each language.

Participant 4: Classifying personal music collection

Participant 4 is a male participant from The Netherlands in the age group 13-17. The participant has chosen a classification task in which the classifier attempts to distinguish between 5 different music labels; pop, indie, minecraft, synthwave and 1980. The music collection consists of 80 audio files from the personal collection of the participant.

6 Results

6.1 Objective evaluation results

6.1.1 Overview

In this subsection, the results for the objective evaluation are outlined. For every embedding-dataset pair, 25 simulations are carried for every active learning strategy (i.e. random, CPU, DC), and the results are averaged out. The results for every embedding-dataset pair are presented by means of a table which contains classification accuracies at various iterations, and a graph which shows the progression of average classification accuracies over the course of iterations.

For simulations with the GTZAN dataset, the training set is expanded with 20 data points at every iteration, for the Moods MIREX dataset the training set is iteratively expanded with 5 data points, and for the Freesound Loop Dataset the training set is iteratively expanded with 8 data points. The GTZAN training set is expanded over the course of 40 iterations, the Moods MIREX training set is expanded over the course of 44 iterations, and the Freesound Loop Dataset training set is also expanded over the course of 40 iterations.

The HOLA/theoretical upper bound accuracy curve, as introduced in section 5.1.3, has been computed in the CLAP-Freesound Loop Dataset simulations, and has been mentioned in the table and visualized in the graph in section 6.1.7.

[Thesis document continues on the next page]

6.1.2 MAEST and GTZAN

In the objective evaluation for GTZAN and MAEST, the training set was expanded over the course of 40 iterations, and at each iteration, the training set was expanded with 20 data points.

Algo. (\downarrow) ; Iter. (\rightarrow)	1	3	5	7	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
<i>Non-stratified</i>											
RB	0.597	0.766	0.792	0.806	0.829	0.857	0.873	0.876	0.886	0.890	0.888
DC	0.597	0.762	0.807	0.837	0.869	0.879	0.897	0.901	0.901	0.899	0.889
CPU	0.597	0.769	0.808	0.841	0.863	0.870	0.885	0.888	0.891	0.894	0.888
<i>Stratified</i>											
CPU (S)	0.614	0.766	0.808	0.838	0.861	0.873	0.879	0.884	0.891	0.899	0.890
DC (S)	0.614	0.766	0.796	0.824	0.855	0.875	0.894	0.898	0.897	0.897	0.890
RB (S)	0.614	0.763	0.794	0.805	0.836	0.854	0.872	0.876	0.888	0.894	0.894

Table 2: Classification accuracy progress for MAEST-GTZAN over the course of 40 iterations

The following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms without stratified sampling:

Figure 9: MAEST-GTZAN accuracy curve (non-stratified)

And the following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms with stratified sampling:

Figure 10: MAEST-GTZAN accuracy curve (stratified)

6.1.3 MAEST and Moods MIREX

Algo. (\downarrow) ; Iter. (\rightarrow)	1	3	5	7	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
<i>Non-stratified</i>												
RB	0.236	0.241	0.256	0.273	0.273	0.273	0.275	0.294	0.313	0.310	0.319	0.319
DC	0.236	0.254	0.251	0.248	0.259	0.274	0.256	0.283	0.297	0.310	0.329	0.315
CPU	0.236	0.259	0.257	0.272	0.300	0.297	0.296	0.319	0.312	0.312	0.306	0.318
<i>Stratified</i>												
CPU (S)	0.241	0.238	0.262	0.274	0.291	0.292	0.306	0.320	0.319	0.317	0.319	0.321
DC (S)	0.241	0.245	0.245	0.232	0.263	0.263	0.277	0.295	0.298	0.316	0.325	0.318
RB (S)	0.241	0.240	0.260	0.269	0.282	0.282	0.318	0.313	0.318	0.315	0.309	0.322

Table 3: Classification accuracy progress for MAEST-Moods MIREX over the course of 44 iterations

The following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms without stratified sampling:

Figure 11: MAEST-Moods MIREX accuracy curve (non-stratified)

And the following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms with stratified sampling:

Figure 12: MAEST-Moods MIREX accuracy curve (stratified)

6.1.4 MAEST and Freesound Loop Dataset

Algo. (\downarrow) ; Iter. (\rightarrow)	1	3	5	7	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
<i>Non-stratified</i>											
RB	0.228	0.226	0.240	0.245	0.230	0.245	0.240	0.246	0.246	0.250	0.243
DC	0.228	0.225	0.228	0.228	0.252	0.249	0.249	0.254	0.243	0.239	0.238
CPU	0.228	0.236	0.236	0.246	0.252	0.256	0.246	0.242	0.248	0.238	0.240
<i>Stratified</i>											
RB (S)	0.230	0.221	0.233	0.236	0.238	0.237	0.239	0.238	0.231	0.242	0.240
DC (S)	0.230	0.252	0.234	0.240	0.264	0.248	0.247	0.239	0.250	0.241	0.241
CPU (S)	0.230	0.243	0.246	0.240	0.244	0.241	0.242	0.243	0.242	0.236	0.242

Table 4: Classification accuracy progress for MAEST-Freesound Loop Dataset over the course of 40 iterations

The following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms without stratified sampling:

Figure 13: MAEST-Freesound Loop Dataset accuracy curve (non-stratified)

And the following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms with stratified sampling:

Figure 14: MAEST-Freesound Loop Dataset accuracy curve (stratified)

6.1.5 CLAP and GTZAN

Algo. (\downarrow) ; Iter. (\rightarrow)	1	3	5	7	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
<i>Non-stratified</i>											
RB	0.606	0.710	0.734	0.754	0.778	0.798	0.800	0.806	0.816	0.820	0.829
DC	0.606	0.693	0.733	0.771	0.787	0.810	0.818	0.816	0.824	0.826	0.828
CPU	0.606	0.728	0.754	0.776	0.795	0.803	0.812	0.813	0.814	0.822	0.829
<i>Stratified</i>											
CPU (S)	0.628	0.726	0.752	0.765	0.783	0.796	0.802	0.811	0.815	0.821	0.829
DC (S)	0.628	0.693	0.735	0.755	0.794	0.800	0.812	0.817	0.821	0.826	0.829
RB (S)	0.628	0.690	0.727	0.747	0.763	0.780	0.798	0.808	0.820	0.820	0.829

Table 5: Classification accuracy progress for CLAP-GTZAN over the course of 40 iterations

The following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms without stratified sampling:

Figure 15: CLAP-GTZAN accuracy curve (non-stratified)

And the following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms with stratified sampling:

Figure 16: CLAP-GTZAN accuracy curve (stratified)

6.1.6 CLAP and Moods MIREX

Algo. (↓) ; Iter. (→)	1	3	5	7	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
<i>Non-stratified</i>												
RB	0.360	0.467	0.509	0.537	0.565	0.587	0.585	0.573	0.578	0.566	0.560	0.561
DC	0.360	0.454	0.506	0.532	0.573	0.547	0.580	0.575	0.555	0.567	0.556	0.559
CPU	0.360	0.438	0.485	0.522	0.535	0.566	0.568	0.582	0.585	0.577	0.579	0.559
<i>Stratified</i>												
CPU (S)	0.352	0.422	0.469	0.524	0.528	0.548	0.563	0.564	0.571	0.562	0.563	0.559
DC (S)	0.352	0.508	0.514	0.534	0.555	0.561	0.555	0.572	0.577	0.565	0.571	0.559
RB (S)	0.352	0.451	0.488	0.514	0.549	0.570	0.580	0.594	0.578	0.569	0.568	0.567

Table 6: Classification accuracy progress for CLAP-Moods MIREX over the course of 44 iterations

The following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms without stratified sampling:

Figure 17: CLAP-Moods MIREX accuracy curve (non-stratified)

And the following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms with stratified sampling:

Figure 18: CLAP-Moods MIREX accuracy curve (stratified)

6.1.7 CLAP and Freesound Loop Dataset

For this embedding-dataset combination, the classification accuracies with the HOLA heuristic are calculated and visualized.

Algo. (\downarrow) ; Iter. (\rightarrow)	1	3	5	7	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
<i>Non-stratified</i>											
RB	0.390	0.499	0.542	0.560	0.604	0.601	0.624	0.622	0.639	0.634	0.638
DC	0.390	0.481	0.527	0.544	0.570	0.612	0.620	0.629	0.612	0.632	0.637
CPU	0.390	0.511	0.555	0.577	0.612	0.620	0.634	0.624	0.631	0.631	0.637
<i>Stratified</i>											
CPU (S)	0.432	0.518	0.570	0.598	0.601	0.609	0.607	0.618	0.615	0.626	0.637
DC (S)	0.432	0.528	0.540	0.579	0.583	0.618	0.632	0.633	0.630	0.638	0.637
RB (S)	0.432	0.502	0.546	0.550	0.580	0.604	0.612	0.625	0.614	0.625	0.632
HOLA	0.390	0.537	0.595	0.605	0.642	0.662	0.668	0.672	0.671	0.659	0.637

Table 7: Classification accuracy progress for CLAP-Freesound Loop Dataset over the course of 40 iterations

The following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms without stratified sampling:

Figure 19: CLAP-Freesound Loop Dataset accuracy curve (non-stratified)

And the following graph shows the progression of classification accuracies for the algorithms with stratified sampling:

Figure 20: CLAP-Freesound Loop Dataset accuracy curve (stratified)

6.2 Subjective evaluations

6.2.1 Participant 1

In the following table, the grades which have been provided by participant 1 for the questions from the questionnaire are outlined:

Iteration	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9
0	4	6	5	-	5	4	4	5	2
1	-	-	-	-	-	5	3		-

Table 8: Grades for each question provided by participant 1, measured by a 7-point Likert scale. Takes into account the changing classifier performance over the course of iterations. Participant 1 did not interact with the datatables in the UI.

Additional contributions by the participant

Related to question 5, the participant has pointed out that the embedding space indeed encodes some semantic meaning; the participant has recognized regions which contain songs which are very similar in genre and perceived vibe, with outliers occurring occasionally. Question 4 is not answered, given that the participant did not interact with the datatables during any annotation round.

The participant has provided a collection of songs which he is very fond of. Therefore, hovering over the songs in the 2D plot with audio playback activated was perceived as pleasant, and the participant felt invited to listen through the whole music collection.

The participant has also suggested a number of improvements; first of all, within the 2D plot, the default interaction should be the 'box select' tool, and not the 'zoom in' tool, this would improve the workflow significantly. Furthermore, in the current implementation audio playback cannot be paused, implementing this feature could improve the quality of the UI.

6.2.2 Participant 2

In the following table, the grades which have been provided by participant 2 for the questions from the questionnaire are outlined:

Iteration	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9
0	6	4	3	-	5	4	4	5	3*
1	-	-	-	-	-	5	3	-	-
2	-	-	-	-	-	4	4	-	-

Table 9: Grades for each question provided by participant 2, measured by a 7-point Likert scale. Takes into account the changing classifier performance over the course of iterations. Participant 2 did not interact with the datatables in the UI. *) Due to time constraints the classifier could only be trained for 3 iterations.

Additional contributions by the participant

Participant 2 has been able to identify semantic meaning in the music embedding space; this was reflected by the left upper quadrant having a high amount of harder rock songs, whereas the right quadrants depicted music which are acoustic and more relaxed.

After the initial AL loop iteration, participant 2 pointed out that there was a very high prevalence in 7 as the predicted class, and not many low grades were assigned, even though plenty of data points got a class label depicting a low number. Furthermore, some songs which were subjectively perceived

by the participant to have a low grade, got the highest grade possible, a 9. The participant noted that he could understand why the tracks which were marked as difficult could indeed lead to confusion in the classifier; after adding the tracks to the training set in the next iteration, the classifier was perceived as having improved significantly.

The participant pointed out that audio playback on hover was a good addition to the UI. The participant also provided feedback on future improvements; the selected tool for interacting with the 2D plot (i.e. lasso tool, box select, zoom in, etc.), should remain selected after a data point has been annotated. Furthermore, the boxes with metadata which appear after hovering on a song could have a lower opacity. Moreover, the participant proposed a new feature; the workflow could be possibly improved by allowing users to search by track name, after which the associated data point in the 2D space gets highlighted.

Lastly, the participant pointed out that in order to meaningfully interact with the UI, it was necessary to get explanations for how certain functionalities work in the UI, meaning that in future updates, the functionalities could be explained within the UI in more detail, in order to make the interaction process more intuitive.

6.2.3 Participant 3

In the following table, the grades which have been provided by participant 3 for the questions from the questionnaire are outlined:

Iteration	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9
0	5	4	5	-	4	6	6	3	1

Table 10: *Grades for each question provided by participant 3, measured by a 7-point Likert scale. Participant 3 did not interact with the datatables in the UI.*

Additional contributions by the participant

One of the initial observations of participant 3 was the way in which the languages were grouped; there was a clear cluster of Czech, Slovak, Russian and Serbian, and another cluster containing Belarusian, Ukrainian and Polish, and there was a significant distance between the two clusters in the 2D plot. The participant tried different UMAP seeds, but the global structure did not change much.

Participant 3 has pointed out that for every weather forecast, the characteristics of the audio file vary, as reflected by a difference in levels of background noise, the timbre of the voice of the announcer, and more. Participant 3 hypothesized that the characteristics of the audio recording could be an important contributor to the high classification accuracy, and that the CLAP embedding would not need to necessarily distinguish between language-related utterances and semantics to understand that the audio recording is one language or the other.

The participant pointed out that in most cases, a relatively simple decision boundary could be drawn between the clusters associated with each of the languages, which could possibly contribute to a high classification accuracy after the initial iteration. The participant also pointed out that tracks which were marked as difficult were mostly tracks which got a correct class prediction.

Participant 3 provided feedback for the improvement of the UI in future updates; he suggested that it would be helpful for the workflow to be able to undo annotations.

6.2.4 Participant 4

In the following table, the grades which have been provided by participant 4 for the questions from the questionnaire are outlined:

Iteration	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9
0	6	5	-	3	5	6	6	5	1
1*	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-
2*	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-

Table 11: *Grades for each question provided by participant 4, measured by a 7-point Likert scale. Takes into account the changing classifier performance over the course of iterations. *) The participant has refreshed the plot to provide new annotation data.*

Additional contributions by the participant

Participant 4 has explored the music embedding space, and identified clusters of music tracks by C418, and also a prominent cluster of synthwave music. The participant pointed out that the synthwave music cluster had a high distance to another cluster which contained songs from the 1980s, which was not entirely as expected, due to the similarity in perceived vibe/sound.

The participant found that the performance of the classifier was highly dependent on the data which it could train on; in the first simulation, the classifier prediction were perceived as being very accurate, but after resetting the plot and providing new annotated data points, the classifier seemed to perform worse, even though there was a significant overlap in songs annotated in both the first and the second iteration. Furthermore, the participant found in the third simulation that adding more data did not always yield better predictions; in the third simulation, the participant tried more than 5 annotation rounds, but agreed the most with the predictions after the second or third annotation round.

Participant 4 provided feedback for the improvement of the UI; the participant pointed out that setting a selection tool as default would contribute to a better workflow, and recommended implementing pause on audio playback when a data point is not hovered on anymore. Furthermore, the participant identified the potential of the datatables, but pointed out that the current implementation did not contribute significantly to the overall workflow; he suggested adding the ability to sort by probability per class, out of interest to, for instance, see which songs would be most likely to be classified as Minecraft music. The participant also proposed a new heuristic, which would calculate the average distance from any data point to the rest of the data points, averaged out over a large number of UMAP seeds; although computationally expensive, the heuristic could represent a degree of *uniqueness* of a track with respect to the rest of the music collection.

7 Discussion and future work

7.1 CPU and DC heuristics

As part of this research, the class prediction uncertainty (CPU) and the dataset coverage (DC) heuristics have been implemented. The performance of the heuristics has been measured in two ways; by means of objective evaluations, in which AL loops with heuristic-based candidate selection were performed, and through subjective evaluations, in which participants could choose to be assisted in classification tasks by adding highlighted samples to the training set of the classifier.

The objective evaluations have shown promising results with respect to the performance of the CPU and DC heuristics. In the MAEST-GTZAN (section 6.1.1) simulation, at the 10th AL loop iteration, both the DC and CPU heuristic have contributed to a classification accuracy which is higher by approximately 5%, compared to random sample selection. A similar result is achieved in the CLAP-GTZAN simulation (6.1.4); around the 7th iteration, both heuristic-based AL loops achieve a classification which is also 5% higher, compared to random sample selection.

In some cases, audio embeddings have difficulty in distinguishing between classes, and in those simulations, classification accuracies are reached which are just above random guessing. An example of such a case can be found in the MAEST-Freesound Loop Dataset simulations; in the simulations, there is no strategy which yields significantly higher classification accuracies with respect to the other strategies. This could be consistent with the intuition by Sarasúa et al. in their 2012 research, which emphasized the importance of a dataset having informative samples such that heuristic-based sample selection has a positive influence on the classification accuracy (Sarasúa et al., 2012).

An important finding of this research is that the performance of heuristic-based AL strategies in classification tasks is highly dependent on the chosen dataset and audio embedding. As can be seen in the accuracy curves for the objective evaluations, even if both the CPU and DC heuristics significantly outperform random sample selection, the heuristics interchangeably contribute to higher classification accuracies at different iterations. More research is needed to understand the influence of datasets and audio embeddings on the performance of heuristic-based AL classifiers.

The proposed HOLA algorithm, visualized by the highest accuracy curve in the CLAP-Freesound Loop Dataset graph, shows the untapped potential of the heuristics; at different iterations of the AL loop, different heuristics can be better at identifying informative tracks. Ideally, a policy could be learned in which the classifier can provide informed recommendations on which heuristic for sample selection to choose next; to achieve this, data-driven policy learning approaches such as the one proposed in 2017 by Konyushkova et al. (Konyushkova et al., 2017) could be an interesting direction to explore.

It is likely that other heuristics for sample selection could identify samples which are even more informative, and subsequently yield even higher classification accuracies in early iterations; exploring this direction in future research is worthwhile. The promising results of the proposed CPU and DC heuristics are a good foundation for future research.

7.2 User Interface

The participants which have interacted with the UI have given relatively high grades to the perceived enjoyability of interaction with the UI. However, the UI can be further improved, taking inspiration from both participant feedback and literature on UI design.

In their 2020 research on audio data visualization for interactive sound recognition, Ishibashi et al. put forward a number of insights which can be helpful for the optimisation of UIs for audio annotation tasks; spectrograms have been shown to be advantageous for understanding audio characteristics, especially in combination with other visualisation techniques (Ishibashi et al., 2020). Furthermore,

the semantic meaning of sound can be effectively communicated to the user through additional visual cues such as the video thumbnail and images retrieved from audio-to-image algorithms (Ishibashi et al., 2020).

Furthermore, in the current implementation of the UI, all music embedding representations are shown as unique data points, which may lead to a cluttered visualization of data in the case of large music databases. One idea could be the aggregation of data clouds into combined 'bubbles', which can be clicked, in order to subsequently zoom in on a segment of the data. An interesting example of this idea is already implemented in the 2025 version of geotag-based sound exploration on Freesound (Font et al., 2013).

Figure 21: *Freesound Map of Sounds (2025)*. Retrieved from <https://freesound.org/browse/geotags/>

Other possible features which could be added to the UI in future updates include: data point removal, allowing the user to save logs which show a list of performed actions with timestamp, saving user annotations as a 'checkpoint', allowing the user to choose different values for displayed problematic tracks, per heuristic, and more. More directions can be found in the "Additional contributions by the participant" subsections, in the results of the objective evaluations (section 6).

7.3 Other directions for future research

N400 is a brain wave response traditionally considered to be related to language-semantic processing, in which the maximum amplitude in brain activity is reached after about 400 ms after the onset of a word stimulus which is incongruent with the preceding sequence of words (Gazzaniga et al., 2018). In 2009, Daltrozzo & Schön sought to find out if the N400 effect is also elicited by musical stimuli (Daltrozzo & Schön, 2009). The research by Daltrozzo & Schön yielded the first evidence that musical information can also elicit N400 responses, given that a N400 brain response was observed when 1-second, subjectively semantically unrelated music excerpts were played back-to-back (Koelsch, 2011).

Thus, the N400 brain response, elicited by instant audio previews which are subjectively inconsistent with personal taxonomies, could possibly function as a powerful catalyst for quickly finding outliers or candidates for (re-)annotation. Although out of the scope of this research, examining the relationship between audio previewing and the N400 might be an interesting direction for future research. To my knowledge, the connection between the N400 effect and audio previewing in interactive user interfaces has neither been made or explored in other research yet.

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